

On the Number of Graceful Trees

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Abstract: Applying a relation of graceful trees with permutations, we enumerate non-equivalent graceful trees and get a closed formula for such number in this paper.

Key Words: Graceful tree, labeling, permutation.

AMS(2000): 05C10, 05C25, 11C08.

§1. Introduction

For a simple graph $G = (V(G), E(G))$, a vertex *labeling* of G is a mapping $\theta : V(G) \rightarrow \mathbf{Z}$ of non-negative integers that induces for each edge xy a label depending on $\theta(x)$ and $\theta(y)$. A labeling is called a *graceful labeling* of a graph G if it satisfying three conditions following:

- (i) $\forall u, v \in V(G)$, if $u \neq v$, then $\theta(u) \neq \theta(v)$;
- (ii) $\max\{\theta(v) | v \in V(G)\} = |E(G)|$;
- (iii) For $\forall e = xy \in E(G)$, let $\theta(e) = |\theta(x) - \theta(y)|$. Then $\forall e_1, e_2 \in E(G)$, if $e_1 \neq e_2$, then $\theta(e_1) \neq \theta(e_2)$.

Many research works on graph labeling can be found in the reference [2], particularly, graceful graphs. Gracefulness of some graph families can be also seen in references [4] – [10]. In this paper, we concentrate on the enumeration problem of graceful trees with given order.

Let $K_n = (V, E)$ be a complete graph with n vertices $v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n$. All edges of K_n can be denoted by $e_{ij} = v_i v_j$, where $i, j \in N = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$, ($i \neq j$). We denote the vertex labeling of v_i by $\theta(v_i)$, and label it with $\theta(v_i) = i$. Then all edges labeling are respective $\theta(v_n v_1) = n - 1$, $\theta(v_n v_2) = n - 2$, $\theta(v_{n-1} v_1) = n - 2, \dots, \theta(v_n v_{n-1}) = 1$, $\theta(v_{n-1} v_{n-2}) = 1, \dots, \theta(v_2 v_1) = 1$. Obviously, all edge labels $\theta(v_i v_j)$ make up $(n - 1)!$ graceful graphs. Certainly, these graceful graphs include disconnected and isomorphic graphs.

If all edges e_{ij} correspond to coordinates (x_i, y_j) on a Euclidean plane by $x_i = i, y_j = j$ for $1 < i \leq n, 1 \leq j < n$, then there is a bijection between e_{ij} and (x_i, y_j) . Its diagram is a lower triangle with $y = x - a$ for $a = 1, 2, \dots, n - 1$, and the graceful label $\theta(e)$ of an edge e is on the oblique line $y = x - a$.

For example, let $G = K_6$. Its diagram can be found in Fig.1.1.

¹Received September 30, 2007. Accepted January 28, 2008

Fig.1.1

In this diagram, if $\theta(e) = 1$, then $\theta(e) \in \{|x - y| : 2 - 1, 3 - 2, 4 - 3, 5 - 4, 6 - 5\}$. If $\theta(e) = 2$, then $\theta(e) \in \{|x - y| : 3 - 1, 4 - 2, 5 - 3, 6 - 4\}$. $\dots$, If $\theta(e) = 6 - 1$, then $\theta(e) \in \{|x - y| : 6 - 1\}$. In other words, there are 5 oblique lines on Fig.1 when $n = 6$. Suppose these lines are L_1, L_2, L_3, L_4, L_5 . Let (x_{li}, y_{lj}) be a point on the plane with the coordinate (x_i, y_j) and l denotes l -th oblique line. Then $\{(x_{16}, y_{11}) = (6, 1)\} \in L_1$, $\{(x_{25}, y_{21}) = (5, 1), (x_{26}, y_{22}) = (6, 2)\} \in L_2$, $\{(x_{34}, y_{31}) = (4, 1), (x_{35}, y_{32}) = (5, 2), (x_{36}, y_{33}) = (6, 3)\} \in L_3$, $\dots, \{(x_{52}, y_{51}) = (2, 1), (x_{53}, y_{52}) = (3, 2), (x_{54}, y_{53}) = (4, 3), (x_{55}, y_{54}) = (5, 4), (x_{56}, y_{55}) = (6, 5)\} \in L_5$. Moreover, we define

$$y_{11}(y_{21} + y_{22}) \cdots (y_{n-1,1} + y_{n-1,2} + \cdots + y_{n-1,n-1}) = \sum y_{1j_1} y_{2j_2} \cdots y_{n-1,j_{n-1}}, \quad (1)$$

$$x_{1,n}(x_{2,n-1} + x_{2,n}) \cdots (x_{n-1,2} + x_{n-1,3} + \cdots + x_{n-1,n}) = \sum x_{1j_1} x_{2j_2} \cdots x_{n-1,j_{n-1}}. \quad (2)$$

The expansion of these polynomials (1) and (2) both have $(n-1)!$ terms. Terms $\prod_{r=1}^{n-1} x_{s_r, i_r}$ and $\prod_{r=1}^{n-1} y_{s_r, j_r}$ in their expansion are called the *correspondent term pair*, denoted by $(x, y) = (\prod_{r=1}^{n-1} x_{s_r, i_r}, \prod_{r=1}^{n-1} y_{s_r, j_r})$. Then each pair (x, y) corresponds to a graceful graph as just explained.

In a labeling graph G , if a vertex labeling $v_i = n - i + 1$ is replaced by $v_i = i$, then all edge labels are invariant. This kind of labeling are called *equivalent*, seeing in Fig 1.2 for details, in where, $(a \rightarrow a'$ and $b \rightarrow b')$.

Fig.1.2

For instance, choose $n = 4$ in (1) and (2), i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} & y_{11}(y_{21} + y_{22})(y_{31} + y_{32} + y_{33}) \\ &= y_{11}y_{21}y_{31} + y_{11}y_{21}y_{32} + y_{11}y_{21}y_{33} + y_{11}y_{22}y_{31} + y_{11}y_{22}y_{32} + y_{11}y_{22}y_{33} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & x_{14}(x_{23} + x_{24})(x_{32} + x_{33} + x_{34}) \\
 &= x_{14}x_{23}x_{32} + x_{14}x_{23}x_{33} + x_{14}x_{23}x_{34} + x_{14}x_{24}x_{32} + x_{14}x_{24}x_{33} + x_{14}x_{24}x_{34}
 \end{aligned}$$

If $(x, y) = (x_{14}x_{23}x_{32}, y_{11}y_{21}y_{31})$, we get $x_{14} - y_{11} = 3, x_{23} - y_{21} = 2, x_{32} - y_{31} = 1$. Hence (x, y) is correspondent to a graceful star graph.

If $(x, y) = (x_{14}x_{23}x_{33}, y_{11}y_{21}y_{32})$, we find $x_{14} - y_{11} = 3, x_{23} - y_{21} = 2, x_{33} - y_{32} = 1$, which is correspondent to a graceful path graph.

If $(x, y) = (x_{14}x_{23}x_{34}, y_{11}y_{21}y_{33})$, we have $x_{14} - y_{11} = 3, x_{23} - y_{21} = 2, x_{34} - y_{33} = 1$. It is correspondent to a graceful triangular graph.

Notice that by definition, these two labeling in pairs $(x, y) = (x_{14}x_{24}x_{32}, y_{11}y_{22}y_{31})$ and $(x, y) = (x_{14}x_{23}x_{34}, y_{11}y_{21}y_{33})$, $(x, y) = (x_{14}x_{24}x_{33}, y_{11}y_{22}y_{32})$ and $(x, y) = (x_{14}x_{23}x_{33}, y_{11}y_{21}y_{32})$, $(x, y) = (x_{14}x_{24}x_{34}, y_{11}y_{22}y_{33})$ and $(x, y) = (x_{14}x_{23}x_{32}, y_{11}y_{21}y_{31})$ are equivalent.

§2. The Enumeration of Graceful Trees

For enumerating graceful trees, a well-known result is useful.

Lemma 2.1([3]) *Let $T = \{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_{n-1}\}$ be a set of $n - 1$ involutions on $N = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$. Then the product $t_1 t_2 \dots t_{n-1}$ is an n -cyclic permutation if and only if (N, T) is a tree.*

From Lemma 2.1 we obtain a result in the following.

Theorem 2.1 *Let (x, y) be a correspondent term pair. If it is an n -cyclic permutation, then (x, y) corresponds to a graceful tree.*

Proof From the formulae (1) and (2), we have y_{11} and $x_{1n} \rightarrow (x_{1n}, y_{11}), y_{21}$ and $x_{2,n-1} \rightarrow (x_{2,n-1}, y_{21}), y_{22}$ and $x_{2,n} \rightarrow (x_{2,n}, y_{22}), \dots$, etc.. They satisfy $y = x - a, a = 1, 2, \dots, n - 1$. So $(x, y) = (\prod_{r=1}^{n-1} x_{s_r, i_r}, \prod_{r=1}^{n-1} y_{s_r, j_r})$, namely $\{\theta(x, y)\} = \{1, 2, \dots, n - 1\}$. Now if it is n -cyclic permutation (not exist less than n), then it is correspondent to a connected graph of n vertices with $n - 1$ edges by the Lemma 2.1. Therefore it is a graceful tree. $\square$

Corollary 2.1 *A correspondent term pair (x, y) is a graceful tree only if*

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^{n-1} x_i \bigcup_{j=1}^{n-1} y_j = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}.$$

Define a matrix A by

$$A = [a_{xy}],$$

where $a_{xy} = (x, y)$. This matrix shows that there are $(n - 1)!/2$ labeling ways on graceful graphs, but in which $(n - 2)!/2$ labeling ways are equivalent. We need to delete the pair $(2, n)$ in the matrix A . This is tantamount to cancel equivalent labeling. In addition, the three pairs $(1, n), (1, n - 1)$ and $(n - 1, n)$ consist of a 3-cyclic with an edge set $\{e_{1n}, e_{1,n-1}, e_{n-1,n}\}$. In other words, there are $(n - 2)!/2$ graceful graphs contain 3-cyclic with edge $e_{n-1,n}$, correspondent to

the pair $(n-1, n)$. Hence cancel the pair $(n-1, n)$ in the matrix A . So we get a new matrix A' from A .

According to the previous discussions, define a permutation

$$T(n) = \begin{pmatrix} y_1 & y_2 & \cdots & y_{n-1} \\ x_1 & x_2 & \cdots & x_{n-1} \end{pmatrix},$$

where $y_1 = y_2 = 1, x_1 = n, x_2 = n-1$. Then we have the next result.

Theorem 2.2 For an integer $n \geq 3$,

- (i) if $y_{i+1} = y_i$ or $y_{i+1} = y_i + 1$ for all indexes i , then $T(n)$ corresponds to a graceful tree;
- (ii) if there is an integer k such that $y_i = y_{i+1}$ and $y_{i+2} = y_i + 1, y_{i+3} = y_i + 2, \dots, y_{i+k} = y_i + k - 1$, rearrange y_j such that the j -th entry is $y'_j \leq j$ for $i+2 \leq j \leq i+k$ and define $x'_j = y'_j + n - j$. Then the new pair (x', y') , namely

$$T'(n) = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & y'_3 & y'_4 & \cdots & y'_{n-1} \\ n & n-1 & x'_3 & x'_4 & \cdots & x'_{n-1} \end{pmatrix}$$

is still correspondent to a graceful tree.

Proof The case of $y_3 = y_4 = \dots = y_{n-1} = 1$ and $x_i = n - i + 1, i = 3, 4, \dots, n-1$ is trivial, which corresponds to a star tree.

We verify Theorem 2.2(i) in the first. When $y_1 = y_2 = 1, x_1 = n, x_2 = n-1$, so v_1, v_{n-1} and v_n three vertices consist of a path. When $y_i = y_{i+1}, x_i = y_i + n - i$, then $x_{i+1} = y_i + n - i - 1 = x_i - 1$. When $y_{i+1} = y_i + 1, x_i = y_i + n - i$, then $x_{i+1} = x_i$. So for any integer $i, 1 \leq i \leq n$, we know that $y_{i+1} = y_i + 1 \rightarrow x_{i+1} = x_i; y_{i+1} = y_i \rightarrow x_{i+1} = x_i - 1$, i.e., $0 \leq |y_{i+1} - y_i| \leq 1, 0 \leq |x_{i+1} - x_i| \leq 1$ and $x_{n-1} - y_{n-1} = 1$. Thereafter,

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^{n-1} y_i \bigcup_{j=1}^{n-1} x_j = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}.$$

Because three vertices v_1, v_{n-1} and v_n consist of a path. When $y_3 = y_2 = y_1 = 1$, we obtain $x_3 = n-2$. So v_{n-2} and v_1 are connected. Similarly, if $y_3 = 2, x_3 = n-1, v_2$ and v_{n-1} are connected. In fact, for any integer $i, 1 \leq i \leq n$, we have $y_{i+1} = y_i \rightarrow x_{i+1} = x_i + 1$ or $y_{i+1} = y_i + 1 \rightarrow x_{i+1} = x_i$. If $y_{i+1} = y_i$, then y_{i+1} and y_i corresponds to same vertex v_s, x_{i+1} corresponds to vertex v_t, v_s and v_t are connected, by $x_i = y_i + n - i$. Similarly, if $x_{i+1} = x_i$, then x_{i+1} and x_i corresponds to same vertex v_t, y_{i+1} corresponds to vertex v_s, v_s and v_t are connected. we know that $T(n)$ corresponds to a graceful tree by Lemma 2.1.

For Theorem 2.2(ii), let $N = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$. If $y_i = y_{i+1}, x_{i+1} = x_i - 1$ and $y_{i+2}, y_{i+3}, \dots, y_{i+k}$ are consecutive plus 1 of y_i , then $x_{i+2} = x_{i+3} = \dots = x_{i+k} = x_{i+1}$. Since y_{i+1} does not participate in the rearrangement, we know that $x_{i+1} = y_{i+1} + n - i + 1$. Notice that $y_{i+2}, y_{i+3}, \dots, y_{i+k}$ participating in the rearrangement do not change these labels of n vertices. Namely, the labeling set $\{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ is not dependent on $x_{i+2}, x_{i+3}, \dots, x_{i+k}$ by $x_{i+2} = x_{i+3} = \dots = x_{i+k} = x_{i+1}$. In fact, $y_{i+2}, y_{i+3}, \dots, y_{i+k}$ correspond to $k-1$ leaves of a tree, and

$\min\{x_i\} = x_{n-1} > \max\{y_i\} = y_{n-1}, i = 1, 2, \dots, n$. If y_{i+r} is replaced by $y_{i+r-j}(1 \leq j \leq r-2)$ for $2 \leq i \leq k$, then $y_{i+r} > y_{i+r-j}$. We obtain $x'_{i+r-j} > x_{i+r-j} = x_{i+1}$, since there exists an $x_s = x'_{i+r-j}(x_1 \geq x_s \geq x_{i+1})$ correspondent to a vertex of a tree, which does not change these y_{i+r} correspondent to leaves. If y_{i+r} is replaced by $y_{i+r+j}(1 \leq j \leq k-r)$, we obtain $x'_{i+r+j} = y_{i+r} + n - i - r - j < x_{i+r+j} = x_{i+1}$. If $x'_{i+r+j} \geq x_{n-1}$, there exists an $x_s = x'_{i+r+j}(x_{i+1} \geq x_s \geq x_{n-1})$. Now if $x'_{i+r+j} \leq y_{n-1}$, then there still exists a $y_t = x'_{i+r+j}$. Both of them do not change these y_{i+r} correspondent to leaves. Therefore,

$$T'(n) = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & y'_3 & y'_4 & \cdots & y'_{n-1} \\ n & n-1 & x'_3 & x'_4 & \cdots & x'_{n-1} \end{pmatrix}.$$

still corresponds to a graceful tree. □

According to Theorem 2.2, the rearrangement on y_i enable us to get new graceful tree, is not equivalent to the original tree. We enumerate all rearrangement labeling on graceful trees in the following.

Let $T(1^2, 2^2, 3^2, \dots, k^{r_0})$ denote a permutation

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & y_3 & y_4 & \cdots & y_{n-1} \\ n & n-1 & x_3 & x_4 & \cdots & x_{n-1} \end{pmatrix},$$

in which, $y_1 = y_2, y_3 = y_4, \dots, y_{2i-1} = y_{2i} = i$ for $i \leq k$. Let $E(T_n)$ denote the number of all non-equivalent graceful trees of n vertices, and $E(T_n, k^{r_0})$ denote the number of permutations on $k+1, k+2, \dots, n-k-r_0+1$ satisfying $y_i \leq i$ and $x_i = y_i + n - i$ for $k+1 \leq i \leq n-k-r_0+1$. Applying Theorem 2.2 we find the following result.

Theorem 2.3 *For any integer $n > 2$, let $E(T_n, K) = \sum_{1 \leq k \leq \frac{n}{2}} E(T_n, k^{r_0})$. If $n \equiv 0(mod 2)$, then*

$$\begin{aligned} E(T_n, K) &= \sum_{i=2}^{\alpha} i^{n-3i+2} (i^{i-1} - 1) \cdot (i-2)! \\ &+ \sum_{i=1}^{\beta-1} (\alpha+i) ((\alpha+i)^{\alpha-2i+1} - 1) \cdot (\alpha+i-2)! \\ &+ \sum_{i=1}^{\gamma} (2i-1) \cdot \left(\frac{n}{2} - i\right)! + (\alpha-1) \sum_{i=0}^{\lambda} i! \\ &+ \sum_{i=1}^{\beta} i(\alpha-2i+\rho+2) \cdot (\alpha-2i+\rho)!, \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

where,

$$\begin{cases} \alpha = \frac{n}{3}, \beta = \frac{n}{6}, \gamma = \frac{n}{6}, \lambda = \frac{n}{3} - 1, \rho = 0, & \text{if } n \equiv 0(mod 6); \\ \alpha = \frac{n-1}{3}, \beta = \frac{n+2}{6}, \gamma = \frac{n-4}{6}, \lambda = \frac{n-1}{3}, \rho = 1, & \text{if } n \equiv -2(mod 6); \\ \alpha = \frac{n+1}{3}, \beta = \frac{n-2}{6}, \gamma = \frac{n-2}{6}, \lambda = \frac{n-2}{3}, \rho = -1, & \text{if } n \equiv 2(mod 6). \end{cases}$$

If $n \equiv 1(\text{mod}2)$, then

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(T_n, K) &= \sum_{i=2}^{\alpha'} i^{n-3i+2} (i^{i-1} - 1) \cdot (i - 2)! \\
 &+ \sum_{i=1}^{\beta'} ((\alpha' + i)^{\alpha'-2i} - 1) \cdot (\alpha' + i - 2)! \\
 &+ \sum_{i=1}^{\gamma'} (2i - 1) \cdot \left(\frac{n-1}{2} - i\right)! + (\alpha' - 1) \sum_{i=0}^{\lambda'} i! \\
 &+ \sum_{i=1}^{\beta'} i(\alpha' - 2i + \rho' + 2) \cdot (\alpha' - 2i + \rho')! + \beta' + 1, \tag{4}
 \end{aligned}$$

where,

$$\begin{cases} \alpha' = \frac{n+1}{3}, \beta' = \frac{n-5}{6}, \gamma' = \frac{n+1}{6}, \lambda' = \frac{n+1}{3} - 2, \rho' = -1, & \text{if } n \equiv -1(\text{mod}6); \\ \alpha' = \frac{n}{3}, \beta' = \frac{n-3}{6}, \gamma' = \frac{n-3}{6}, \lambda' = \frac{n}{3} - 1, \rho' = 0, & \text{if } n \equiv 3(\text{mod}6); \\ \alpha' = \frac{n+2}{3}, \beta' = \frac{n-7}{6}, \gamma' = \frac{n-1}{6}, \lambda' = \frac{n-4}{3}, \rho' = -2, & \text{if } n \equiv 2(\text{mod}6). \end{cases}$$

Proof Let $k = 1, r_0 = 2$. Then

$$T(1^2) = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 & \cdots & n-2 \\ n & n-1 & n-1 & n-1 & n-1 & \cdots & n-1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

In fact, it is correspondent to a graceful tree(see Fig.2.1 below).

If $y_3 \neq 2$, then $y_3 = 3$ because $x_i = y_i + n - i$ and $\max\{x_i\} = n$. Similarly, if $y_4 \neq 2$ too, then $y_4 = 4$. If there is an integer $r, 3 \leq r \leq n - 1$ such that $y_r = 2$, then $y_i = i, x_i = n$ for $3 \leq i < r$. In other word, only $y_3 = 2$ or $y_3 = 3$, and y_4 is one element of the set $\{2, 3, 4\} - \{y_3\}$, y_5 is one element of the set $\{2, 3, 4, 5\} - \{y_3, y_4\}, \dots$. Continuing this process, y_{n-1} is uniquely determined at the final. Hence the number of permutations is $2 \times 2 \times 2 \times \cdots \times 2 \times 1 = 2^{n-4}$.

When

$$T(1^3) = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 2 & 3 & \cdots & n-3 \\ n & n-1 & n-2 & n-2 & n-2 & \cdots & n-2 \end{pmatrix},$$

then choose an element y_4 in the set $\{2, 3, 4\}$, an element y_5 in the set $\{2, 3, 4, 5\} - \{y_4\}, \dots$. Continuing in this manner, y_{n-2} and y_{n-1} are 2 selectable. So the number of such permutations is $3 \times 3 \times 3 \times \cdots \times 3 \times 2! = 3^{n-6} \cdot 2!$.

Similarly, When

$$T(1^4) = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 2 & 3 & \cdots & n-4 \\ n & n-1 & n-2 & n-3 & n-3 & n-3 & \cdots & n-3 \end{pmatrix},$$

we have $E(T_n, 1^4) = 4 \times 4 \times 4 \times \cdots \times 4 \times 3! = 4^{n-8} \cdot 3!$ and generally,

$$E(T_n, 1^r) = \begin{cases} r^{n-2r}(r-1)!, & \begin{cases} 2 \leq r \leq \frac{n}{2} - 1, & n \text{ is even;} \\ 2 \leq r \leq \frac{n-1}{2}, & n \text{ is odd.} \end{cases} \\ (n-r-1)!, & \begin{cases} \frac{n}{2} - 1 < r \leq n-1, & n \text{ is even;} \\ \frac{n-1}{2} < r \leq n-1, & n \text{ is odd.} \end{cases} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

In general, if $k + \lceil \frac{k}{2} \rceil \leq \frac{n}{2} - 1$

$$E(T_n, k^r) = \sum_{r=k+1}^{\frac{n}{2} - \lceil \frac{k}{2} \rceil} r^{n-2r-k+1} \cdot (r-1)! + \sum_{r=\frac{n}{2} - \lceil \frac{k}{2} \rceil + 1}^{n-k} (n-k-r)!, \text{ n is even;} \\ E(T_n, k^r) = \sum_{r=k+1}^{\lceil \frac{n-k}{2} \rceil} r^{n-2r-k+1} \cdot (r-1)! + \sum_{r=\lceil \frac{n-k}{2} \rceil + 1}^{n-k} (n-k-r)!, \text{ n is odd.} \quad (6)$$

If $k + \lceil \frac{k}{2} \rceil > \frac{n}{2} - 1$

$$E(T_n, k^r) = \begin{cases} \sum_{r=1}^{n-2k} (n-2k-r)!, & n \text{ is even;} \\ \sum_{r=1}^{n-2k-1} (n-2k-r)!, & n \text{ is odd.} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

By (6) and (7), when n is even, define

$$f(k) = \sum_{r=k+1}^{\frac{n}{2} - \lceil \frac{k}{2} \rceil} r^{n-2r-k+1} \cdot (r-1)!$$

with $k \in \{\frac{n}{3} - 1, \frac{n-1}{3} - 1, \frac{n+1}{3} - 1\}$. Then we know that

(a) if $n \equiv 0 \pmod{6}$, $k = \frac{n}{3} - 1$, then

$$f\left(\frac{n}{3} - 1\right) = \left(\frac{n}{3}\right)^2 \left(\frac{n}{3} - 1\right)!;$$

(b) if $n \equiv -2 \pmod{6}$, $k = \frac{n-1}{3} - 1$, then

$$f\left(\frac{n-1}{3} - 1\right) = \left(\frac{n-1}{3}\right)^3 \left(\frac{n-1}{3} - 1\right)! + \left(\frac{n-1}{3} + 1\right) \left(\frac{n-1}{3}\right)!;$$

(c) if $n \equiv 2 \pmod{6}$, $k = \frac{n}{3} - 1$, then

$$f\left(\frac{n+1}{3} - 1\right) = \left(\frac{n+1}{3}\right) \left(\frac{n+1}{3} - 1\right)!.$$

Whence we obtain that

$$\sum_{i=2}^{r < \frac{n+1}{3}} (i^{n-2i} + i^{n-2i-1} + i^{n-2i-2} + \cdots + i^{n-3i+2})(i-1)! = \sum_{i=2}^{r < \frac{n+1}{3}} i^{n-3i+2}(i^{i-1} - 1)(i-2)! \quad (8)$$

When $n \equiv 0(\text{mod}6)$,

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{i=1}^{\frac{n}{6}-1} \left(\left(\frac{n}{3} + i\right)^1 + \left(\frac{n}{3} + i\right)^2 + \left(\frac{n}{3} + i\right)^3 + \cdots + \left(\frac{n}{3} + i\right)^{\frac{n}{3}-2i+1} \right) \left(\frac{n}{3} + i - 1\right)! \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^{\frac{n}{6}-1} \left(\frac{n}{3} + i\right) \left(\left(\frac{n}{3} + i\right)^{\left(\frac{n}{3}-2i+1\right)} - 1\right) \left(\frac{n}{3} + i - 2\right)!. \end{aligned}$$

We obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{k+\lceil \frac{k}{2} \rceil \leq \frac{n}{2}-1} \sum_{r=k+1}^{\frac{n}{2}-\lceil \frac{k}{2} \rceil} r^{n-2r-k+1}(r-1)! \\ &= \sum_{i=2}^{\frac{n}{3}} i^{n-3i+2}(i^{i-1} - 1)(i-2)! + \sum_{i=1}^{\frac{n}{6}-1} \left(\frac{n}{3} + i\right) \left(\left(\frac{n}{3} + i\right)^{\left(\frac{n}{3}-2i+1\right)} - 1\right) \left(\frac{n}{3} + i - 2\right)!. \quad (9) \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, when $n \equiv -2(\text{mod}6)$,

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{k+\lceil \frac{k}{2} \rceil \leq \frac{n}{2}-1} \sum_{r=k+1}^{\frac{n}{2}-\lceil \frac{k}{2} \rceil} r^{n-2r-k+1}(r-1)! \\ &= \sum_{i=2}^{\frac{n-1}{3}} i^{n-3i+2}(i^{i-1} - 1)(i-2)! \\ &+ \sum_{i=1}^{\frac{n-4}{6}} \left(\frac{n-1}{3} + i\right) \left(\left(\frac{n-1}{3} + i\right)^{\left(\frac{n-1}{3}-2i+1\right)} - 1\right) \left(\frac{n-1}{3} + i - 2\right)!, \quad (10) \end{aligned}$$

and when $n \equiv 2(\text{mod}6)$,

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{k+\lceil \frac{k}{2} \rceil \leq \frac{n}{2}-1} \sum_{r=k+1}^{\frac{n}{2}-\lceil \frac{k}{2} \rceil} r^{n-2r-k+1}(r-1)! \\ &= \sum_{i=2}^{\frac{n+1}{3}} i^{n-3i+2}(i^{i-1} - 1)(i-2)! \\ &+ \sum_{i=1}^{\frac{n-8}{6}} \left(\frac{n+1}{3} + i\right) \left(\left(\frac{n+1}{3} + i\right)^{\left(\frac{n+1}{3}-2i+1\right)} - 1\right) \left(\frac{n+1}{3} + i - 2\right)!. \quad (11) \end{aligned}$$

Now let

$$f_1(k) = \sum_{r=\frac{n}{2}-\lceil\frac{k}{2}\rceil+1}^{n-k} (n-k-r)!.$$

Similarly, we get that

(a) When $n \equiv 0(\text{mod}6)$, $k = \frac{n}{3} - 1$,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{r=\frac{n}{2}-\lceil\frac{k}{2}\rceil+1}^{n-k} (n-k-r)! &= \sum_{i=1}^{\frac{n}{3}-1} f_1(i) \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^{\frac{n}{6}} (2i-1)\left(\frac{n}{2}-i\right)! + \left(\frac{n}{3}-1\right) \sum_{i=0}^{\frac{n}{3}-1} i!. \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

(b) When $n \equiv -2(\text{mod}6)$, $k = \frac{n-1}{3} - 1$,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{r=\frac{n}{2}-\lceil\frac{k}{2}\rceil+1}^{n-k} (n-k-r)! &= \sum_{i=1}^{\frac{n-1}{3}-1} f_1(i) \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^{\frac{n-4}{6}} (2i-1)\left(\frac{n}{2}-i\right)! + \left(\frac{n-1}{3}-1\right) \sum_{i=0}^{\frac{n-1}{3}-1} i!. \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

(c) When $n \equiv 2(\text{mod}6)$, $k = \frac{n+1}{3} - 1$,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{r=\frac{n}{2}-\lceil\frac{k}{2}\rceil+1}^{n-k} (n-k-r)! &= \sum_{i=1}^{\frac{n+1}{3}-1} f_1(i) \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^{\frac{n-2}{6}} (2i-1)\left(\frac{n}{2}-i\right)! + \left(\frac{n+1}{3}-1\right) \sum_{i=0}^{\frac{n+1}{3}-1} i!. \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

When $k + \lceil\frac{k}{2}\rceil > \frac{n}{2} - 1$. Let

$$f_2(k) = \sum_{r=1}^{n-2k} (n-2k-r)!.$$

We know that

(a) When $n \equiv 0(\text{mod}6)$, $k > \frac{n}{3} - 1$,

$$\sum f_2(k \geq \frac{n}{3}) = \sum_{i=1}^{\frac{n}{6}} i\left(\frac{n}{3}-2i+2\right)\left(\frac{n}{3}-2i\right)!. \quad (15)$$

(b) When $n \equiv -2(\text{mod}6)$, $k > \frac{n-1}{3} - 1$,

$$\sum f_2(k \geq \frac{n-1}{3}) = \sum_{i=1}^{\frac{n+2}{6}} i(\frac{n-1}{3} - 2i + 3)(\frac{n-1}{3} - 2i + 1)! \tag{16}$$

(c) When $n \equiv 2(mod6)$, $k > \frac{n+1}{3} - 1$,

$$\sum f_2(k \geq \frac{n+1}{3}) = \sum_{i=1}^{\frac{n-2}{6}} i(\frac{n+1}{3} - 2i + 1)(\frac{n+1}{3} - 2i - 1)! \tag{17}$$

To sum up, we obtain (3) by formulae (9), (10), (11), (12), (13), (14), (15), (16) and (17).

Similarly, the discussion for the case $n \equiv 1(mod2)$ can be divided into three subcases, i.e., $n \equiv -1(mod6)$, $k = \frac{n-2}{3}$, $n \equiv 3(mod6)$, $k = \frac{n}{3} - 1$ and $n \equiv 1(mod6)$, $k = \frac{n-4}{3}$, and the formula (4) can be found as the formula (3). $\square$

For example, $E(T_6, K) = 10$ when $n = 6$. We obtain 10 non-equivalent graceful trees by permutations following.

$$\begin{aligned} & \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \\ 6 & 5 & 5 & 5 & 5 \end{pmatrix} \rightarrow \{e_{16}, e_{15}, e_{25}, e_{35}, e_{45}\}; & \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 2 & 4 & 3 \\ 6 & 5 & 5 & 6 & 4 \end{pmatrix} \rightarrow \{e_{16}, e_{15}, e_{25}, e_{46}, e_{34}\}; \\ & \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 3 & 2 & 4 \\ 6 & 5 & 6 & 4 & 5 \end{pmatrix} \rightarrow \{e_{16}, e_{15}, e_{36}, e_{24}, e_{45}\}; & \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 3 & 4 & 2 \\ 6 & 5 & 6 & 6 & 3 \end{pmatrix} \rightarrow \{e_{16}, e_{15}, e_{36}, e_{46}, e_{23}\}; \\ & \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 6 & 5 & 4 & 4 & 4 \end{pmatrix} \rightarrow \{e_{16}, e_{15}, e_{14}, e_{24}, e_{34}\}; & \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 3 & 2 \\ 6 & 5 & 4 & 5 & 3 \end{pmatrix} \rightarrow \{e_{16}, e_{15}, e_{14}, e_{35}, e_{23}\}; \\ & \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 2 \\ 6 & 5 & 4 & 3 & 3 \end{pmatrix} \rightarrow \{e_{16}, e_{15}, e_{14}, e_{13}, e_{23}\}; & \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 6 & 5 & 4 & 3 & 3 \end{pmatrix} \rightarrow \{e_{16}, e_{15}, e_{14}, e_{13}, e_{12}\}; \\ & \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 2 & 2 & 3 \\ 6 & 5 & 5 & 4 & 4 \end{pmatrix} \rightarrow \{e_{16}, e_{15}, e_{25}, e_{24}, e_{34}\}; & \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 2 & 2 & 2 \\ 6 & 5 & 5 & 4 & 3 \end{pmatrix} \rightarrow \{e_{16}, e_{15}, e_{25}, e_{24}, e_{23}\}. \end{aligned}$$

When n is a large number, $E(T_n) \gg E(T_n, K)$. Of course, there exist a lot of isomorphic trees in the previous enumeration. We have verified the number of non-isomorphic graceful paths P_n for $n \leq 13$ vertices in the following table.

n	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
$E(P_n)$	1	1	1	2	6	8	10	30	74	162	330	760

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